

Microwave irradiation in organic synthesis towards the construction of biologically active *N*-heterocycles

Rajiv Karmakar^{a,b} and Chhanda Mukhopadhyay^{a*}

^aDepartment of Chemistry, University of Calcutta, 92, Acharya Prafulla Chandra Road, Kolkata-700 009, India

^bDepartment of Chemistry, Dum Dum Motijheel College (West Bengal State University), Kolkata-700 074, India

E-mail: cmukhop@yahoo.co.in, rajivkarmakar84@gmail.com

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In the past few years, using microwave energy to heat and drive chemical reactions has become progressively more popular theme in the scientific community. Microwave-assisted organic synthesis is proving to be instrumental in the rapid synthesis of compounds with novel and improved biological activities. An efficiency of 'microwave flash heating' for chemical synthesis is the spectacular reduction in reaction times from days and hours to minutes and seconds, higher yields under milder reaction conditions, and higher product purities etc. Multicomponent reactions are precious tools for the making of various *N*-heterocycles and the *N*-heterocyclic scaffolds represent the central framework of many biologically active compounds. *N*-containing heterocycles hold a special place among pharmaceutically significant natural products and synthetic compounds needed for any developed human society. In the fields of organic chemistry, microwave irradiation is rapidly substituted the conventional heating methods in the world of multicomponent chemistry. In this review, we discuss only formation of *N*-containing heterocyclic compounds and their fused analogues under microwave activation using modern organic transformations including cyclocondensation, cycloaddition, multicomponents and other modular reactions.

Keywords: Microwave-assisted synthesis, bio-active molecules, cycloaddition, cyclocondensation, *N*-containing heterocycles, multicomponent reactions, one-pot reactions.

1. Introduction

Organic chemists are engaged to generate a various type of innovative array of organic molecules using eco-friendly conditions. Microwave heating chemistry has blossomed into a powerful technique to promote a diversity of applications in chemical reactions, transformations and synthesis of *N*-heterocycles¹. *N*-containing heterocycles are structural components of many bioactive natural products such as vitamins, alkaloids, hormones, glycosides, antibiotics, and many more compounds which are of significance for human and animal health^{1b}. The technical accessibility (in terms of low costs and simplicity in processing and handling) and make use of extremely mild conditions to carry out the reactions, associated to the global improvement of the syntheses in terms of rate of conversion (yields), shortened reaction times and lack of side-products, contribute nowadays to the huge popularity of the microwave irradiation in synthetic organic chemistry². While microwave-assisted reactions have rapidly developed in most of organic solvents and also used eco-friendly

methods, which use greener solvents and supported reagents. There are huge examples of the thriving application of microwave-assisted green chemistry to organic synthesis; these consist of the use of benign reaction medium, solvent-free conditions, and the use of solid-supported, reusable catalysts³. According to the synthetic organic chemists, there is increased interest in nonclassical heating technologies and their concepts that facilitate more rapid synthesis and screening of chemical substances to identify compounds with appropriate qualities. Nowadays, one such high-speed technology is microwave-assisted organic synthesis (MAOS). This MAOS technology often facilitates the discovery of novel reaction pathways, because the extreme reaction conditions achievable by microwave heating sometimes lead to abnormal reactivity that cannot always be duplicated by conventional heating. Therefore, lots of academic and industrial research groups are already using MAOS as a forefront non-classical heating technology for rapid optimization of reactions, for the efficient synthesis of novel chemical entities

and for discovering and probing new chemical reactivity⁴.

In this present review, we will discuss the application of two methodologies that can notably contribute to the efficiency of the synthesis of *N*-heterocycles compounds, i.e. multicomponent chemistry and microwave irradiation. The *N*-heterocycle containing molecules are extensively studied for their synthesis and their applications not only in medicinal chemistry, but also in optics, electronics and material sciences^{5,6}. Therefore, the nonclassical heating technologies of microwaves are going to be very important in future synthesis of biologically active *N*-heterocycles.

1.1. MW irradiation

A nonclassical heating technique using microwaves (MWs), termed "Bunsen burner of the 21st century", is rapidly becoming popular and is spectacularly reducing reaction times⁷. The rate of acceleration are observed in microwave irradiation is due to material-wave interactions leading to dielectric heating. The microwave consists of an electric and magnetic field and it is also known as electromagnetic irradiation in the frequency range of 0.3 to 300 GHz. This electromagnetic irradiation can act as a nonionizing radiation that causes molecular motions of ions and rotation of the dipoles, but it does not have an effect on molecular structure⁷. The influence of microwave field causes the molecules, on average to temporarily spend to some extent of extra time oriented themselves in the direction of the electric field rather than in other directions. When the field is removed, thermal

agitation returns the molecules to a disordered state in the relaxation time and thermal energy is released. Therefore, this phenomenon relies on the ability of a specific material or substance to absorb microwave irradiation and convert them into heat^{1e}. This internal heating is much more homogeneous than the classical heating.

1.1a. Effect of MW irradiation on solvents system:

The heating properties of a particular material (solvent) under microwave irradiation conditions are depend on its dielectric properties. The ability of a specific substance to convert electromagnetic irradiation energy into heat at a given frequency and temperature is determined by the loss factor ($\tan \delta$). This loss factor is expressed as the quotient $\tan \delta = \epsilon''/\epsilon'$, where ϵ'' is the dielectric loss, which is directly indicate the efficiency with which electromagnetic radiation is converted into heat, and ϵ' is the dielectric constant describing the ability of molecules to be polarized by the presence electric field. A reaction medium with a high $\tan \delta$ value is required for efficient absorption and rapid heating. The loss factors for few common organic solvents are summarized in Table 1^{1f,4i}.

1.1b. Differences between conventional and microwave heating:

In general most of organic reactions are carried out by normal heating with an external heat source such as an oil bath. This process is a relatively slow and ineffective technique for transferred energy into the reaction system. It de-

Table 1. Loss factors ($\tan \delta$) of different solvents^a

Solvent	$\tan \delta$	Range	Solvent	$\tan \delta$
Ethylene glycol	1.350		DMF	0.161
Ethanol	0.941		1,2-Dichloroethane	0.127
DMSO	0.825		Water	0.123
2-Propanol	0.799		Chlorobenzene	0.101
Formic acid	0.722		Chloroform	0.091
Methanol	0.659		Acetonitrile	0.062
Nitrobenzene	0.589		Ethyl acetate	0.059
1-Butanol	0.571		Acetone	0.054
2-Butanol	0.447		Tetrahydrofuran	0.047
1,2-Dichlorobenzene	0.280		Dichloromethane	0.042
NMP	0.275		Toluene	0.040
Acetic acid	0.174		Hexane	0.020

^aData from Ref. [4i]: 2.45 GHz, 20°C. Additional familiar solvents without a permanent dipole moment such as carbon tetrachloride, benzene, and dioxane are more or less microwave transparent. It has to be emphasized that a low $\tan \delta$ value does not withstand a particular solvent from being used in a microwave-heated reaction.

depends on the thermal conductivity of the various materials that must be penetrated and results in the temperature of the reaction vessel being higher than that of the reaction mixture. In contrast, microwave irradiation produces efficient internal heating by direct coupling of microwave energy with the molecules like solvents, reagents and catalysts that are present in the reaction mixture. Organic reactions that are messy and give only trace amounts of the desired product when carried out by conventional heating, are often cleaner when irradiated in a microwave and provide high amounts of the desired product.

We collect some information about the inverted temperature gradients in microwave versus oil-bath heating from the above mention (Fig. 1). The temperature profiles (modelling) 1 minute after heating by microwave irradiation (left) compared with treatment in an oil-bath (right). Microwave irradiation increases the temperature of the whole volume simultaneously (bulk heating), whereas in the oil-heated tube of the reaction mixture in contact with the vessel wall is heated first.

1.1c. Benefits of microwaves assisted synthesis:

Microwaves can accelerate the rate of reaction, provide

Fig. 1. Inverted temperature gradients in microwave versus oil-bath heating.

better yields and higher purity, uniform heating with lower energy usage, get better reproducibility of reactions and help in developing convenient and cleaner synthetic routes. The main advantages of microwave assisted organic synthesis are in Fig. 2.

1.1d. Limitations of microwave assisted synthesis:

The use of microwaves as a source of heating has limited applicability for materials that absorb them.

Fig. 2. Benefits of MW synthesis.

Microwaves cannot heat the materials such as sulphur, which are transparent to their radiation.

Improper use of microwave heating for rate enhancement of chemical reactions involving radioisotopes may result in uncontrolled radioactive decay.

Microwave irradiation are action involving concentrated sulphuric acid may damage the polymer vessel used for heating.

Conducting microwave reactions at high pressure conditions may also result in uncontrolled reactions and cause explosions.

Microwaves operating at a low frequency range are only able to penetrate the human skin and higher frequency-range microwaves can also reach the body organs.

DNA to high frequency microwaves during a biochemical reaction may result in complete degeneration of the DNA strand^{8,9}.

1.2. Microwave-assisted multicomponent synthesis of heterocycles

Microwave irradiation has very significant effect to promote one pot multicomponent reactions. The heterocycle molecules have many kinds of structural diversity which is enclosed by MCRs process. We focus on the heterocycles ring system that is formed in these reaction pathways and which is classified it by the number and types of heteroatoms are present. Many multicomponent reactions depend on the unique reactivity of enamines, isocyanides, and imines. As a result, the vast majority of heterocyclic multicomponent reaction products are nitrogen heterocycles. In the following sections, these *N*-heterocycles are classified by the

ring size and number of nitrogen atoms in the ring.

This review highlights recent applications of controlled microwave heating technology in synthesis of *N*-heterocycles. The term "controlled" here refers to the use of a dedicated microwave reactor for synthetic chemistry purposes.

1.2.1. Applications of microwaves in the synthesis of heterocycles

1.2.1a. Fused pyrimidine ring formation:

Imidazo[1,2-*a*]pyrimidines are an important class of compounds due to their wide range of biological activity. Derivatives of imidazo[1,2-*a*]pyrimidine have been exposed to act as GABA receptor agonists¹⁰ for the treatment of anxiety disorders and antiproliferative activity¹¹.

Thompson *et al.*¹² reported a regioselective solvent-free protocol towards imidazo-pyrimidines yielding almost exclusively the 2-amino isomer (**A**) (Scheme 1). This solvent-free condensation reactions of 2-aminopyrimidine with aldehydes and isocyanides were carried out under microwave irradiation of 400–800 W at small intervals in the presence of hydrogen zeolite ('zeolite HY') furnishing major product (**A**) in 22–49% and minor product (**B**) (0.0–2.8%) yield. A hydrogen zeolite ('zeolite HY') was found to be a novel and effective promoter for the reaction, generally leading to clean conversion and also permitting use of the normally unreactive 4,6-dimethyl-2-aminopyrimidine.

Pyrimidine is a six-membered ring containing two nitrogen atoms at positions 1 and 3 of the heterocycle. Pyrimidine derivatives usually exhibit a huge variety of biological activities, and could be used in therapy as anti-protozoan agents [e.g. (i) exhibits *in vitro* an MIC value of 0.25 micro-

Scheme 1. Synthesis of fused aminoimidazoles.

Fig. 3. Plausible mechanism for formation of imidazo-pyrimidines.

gm/mL] against *Plasmodium falciparum*¹³, anti-cancer agents (e.g. (ii) is a selective adenosine A1 receptor antagonist¹⁴ and (iii) is a phosphatidylinositol C kinase inhibitor)¹⁵, or as antibacterial agents (e.g. (iv) shows antitubercular activity against *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* at the concentration of 12.5 micro-gm /mL) (Fig. 4)¹⁶.

Fig. 4. Representative examples of bioactive pyrimidines.

Jiang *et al.*¹⁷ have described a new synthetic route for the preparation of highly functionalized thiopyrano-, pyrano[4,3-*d*]pyrimidine derivatives with a benzylic moiety at eight position of a fused pyrimidine nucleus were synthesized through a one-pot four-component reaction of aromatic aldehydes (1), tetrahydrothiopyran-4-one (tetra-hydropyran-4-one) (3), and aryl amidines (2) using *t*-BuOK as a base under microwave heating (Scheme 2) and the reaction mechanistic pathways are shown in Fig. 5. The procedure is

Ar	Ar2
Ph, 4-ClC ₆ H ₄ , 4-OMeC ₆ H ₄ , 4-FC ₆ H ₄ , 4-BrC ₆ H ₄ , 2-Thienyl, 4-Toyl etc.	Ph

Scheme 2. Microwave-assisted synthesis of thiopyran- and pyrano[4,3-*d*]pyrimidines.

Fig. 5. Proposed mechanism for the formation of fused pyrimidines ring.

facile, avoiding time-consuming and costly syntheses, tedious work-up, and purifications of precursors as well as protection/deprotection of functional groups. This method is very efficient due to short reaction times and easy work up and provides a four-component strategy for the construction of the thiopyrano-, and pyrano[4,3-*d*]pyrimidine skeletons.

A novel series of pyridopyrimidines were synthesized by Basiri *et al.*¹⁸ through a one pot four-component MW-assisted reaction under solvent-free condition, involved 4-piperidone hydrochloride monohydrate (1), aromatic aldehydes (2) and urea or thiourea (3) in the presence of catalytic amount of solid sodium ethoxide (Scheme 3). Interestingly, the reactions were completed in 30 seconds, affording the desired product pyridopyrimidines (4) in excellent yields (85–95%) and with a high degree of purity. This reaction proceeds through a domino sequence involving Michael addition, condensation and tautomerization, as outlined in Fig.6.

Ar	Ar2
Ph, 2-MeC ₆ H ₄ , 4-ClC ₆ H ₄ , 4-FC ₆ H ₄ , 4-BrC ₆ H ₄ , 2,4-Cl ₂ C ₆ H ₃ , 2-OMeC ₆ H ₄ , Naphthyl.	

Scheme 3. Synthesis of pyridopyrimidine derivatives under microwave irradiation.

1.2.1b. Pyrroles and its derivatives:

Pyrroles are heterocycles of great importance because pyrrole is a basic substructure of numerous biologically active alkaloids and pharmaceutical products^{19,20}. Classically, pyrroles were synthesized by various methods viz. Knorr pyr-

Fig. 6. Possible mechanism for the formation of pyridopyrimidine.

role synthesis²¹, Paal-Knorr synthesis²², Hantzsch pyrrole synthesis²³ etc.

Cores and Menendez group²⁴ have described the Hantzsch-type microwave-assisted, solvent-free sequential three-component reaction between primary amines (1), β -dicarbonyl compounds (2) and α -bromoesters (3) in the presence of 5% InCl_3 Lewis acid catalyst at temperature 120°C to afford a library of diversely substituted 2-pyrrolin-5-ones in a 40–76% range of yields (Scheme 4) and the reaction mechanistic pathways are shown in Fig. 7.

Fig. 7. Possible mechanism for the formation of 2-pyrrolin-5-one.

R ¹	R ²	R ³	R ⁴
<i>n</i> -Bu, Bu, Me, Allyl, H, 2-Hydroxymethyl	Me, Et, <i>n</i> -Pr	-OEt, -OMe,	H, Ph, Me, Et

Scheme 4. Microwave-assisted multicomponent synthesis of 2-pyrrolin-5-ones.

Microwave-assisted one-pot multicomponent 1,3-dipolar cycloaddition of diethyl aminomalonate or α -amino esters (derived from glycine, alanine, phenylalanine, and phenylglycine) with ethyl glyoxylate and the corresponding dipolarophile such as maleimides, methyl acrylate, methyl fumarate, (*E*)-1,2-bis(phenylsulfonyl)ethylene, and electron deficient alkynes allows the diastereoselective synthesis of new polysubstituted pyrrolidine derivatives in Scheme 5 has been described by Aracil and his co-workers²⁵. Microwave-assisted heating processes give better results than conventional heating ones, affording endo-cycloadducts (4) as major stereoisomers.

1.2.1c. Benzo-derivatives of seven-membered rings:

1,4-Benzodiazepine is related with a huge range of biological properties. These ring systems are incorporated into drugs used for AIDS, cancer, anti-viral treatment etc. 1,4-Benzodiazepine derivatives are well established in the literature as important biologically active compounds. Several 1,4-benzodiazepines are widely used as anti-convulsant²⁶, antianxiety²⁷, sedative²⁸, hypnotic²⁹, neuroleptic agents³⁰ and muscle-relaxants³¹.

De Silva group³² has been described a one-pot, two-step microwave-assisted synthesis towards biologically interesting benzodiazepines. The reaction involves an Ugi-4CR of

Scheme 5. Microwave-assisted synthesis of polysubstituted pyrrolidine derivatives.

amines, aldehydes, isonitriles and carboxylic acids followed by a 7-*exo* aza-Michael cyclization (Scheme 6). Structural diversity is achieved by using either 2-nitrobenzaldehydes or 2-nitrobenzylamines. The reactants were irradiated for 60 min at 150°C in a 3:1 mixture of ethanol and water, and after the addition of iron powder and NH_4Cl the mixture was irradiated for an additional 30–45 min to give the compound (1) with 80–85% yield and compound (2) with 70–85% yield.

Scheme 6. One-pot microwave-assisted synthesis of 1,2,4,5-tetrahydro-1,4-benzodiazepin-3-one.

Fused heterocyclic containing pyrazolopyridine moieties have been described associated with several biological and medicinal activities^{33–36}. Substituted pyrazolo[3,4-*b*]pyridines represent a very important building block in organic synthesis and numerous studies in biological activities such as antileishmanial³⁷, antiviral³⁸ and antibacterial³⁹ promise.

1.2.1d. Fused pyrazolo-pyridine derivatives:

A series of polysubstituted (3'-indolyl)pyrazolo[3,4-*b*]pyridine derivatives were synthesized via one-pot multi-component reactions of 3-cyanoacetyl indoles (1), 3-methyl-1-phenyl-1*H*-pyrazol-5-amine (2) and aldehydes (3) under microwave irradiation in glycol at 150°C for 7–15 min to give the desired product (4) with 67–88% yield. The features of this procedure are mild reaction conditions, high yields, and

operational simplicity have been described by Zhu and his co-workers (Scheme 7)⁴⁰.

Scheme 7. Synthesis of 3'-indolyl pyrazolo-pyridine derivatives under microwave irradiation.

A new series of 2-amino-3,5-dicarbonitrile-6-thio-pyridines derivatives were synthesized successfully by using of an aldehyde, a thiol and two equivalents of malonitrile promoted by ZnCl_2 catalyst under microwave heating and conventional heating have been described by Sridhar *et al.*⁴¹. Microwave irradiation in ethanol at 100°C provides slightly higher yields (46–77%) and far shorter reaction times than conventional heating (Scheme 8) and the reaction mechanistic pathways are shown in Fig. 8.

Scheme 8. Microwave-assisted one-pot synthesis of thiopyridine derivatives.

1.2.1e. Fused indole derivatives:

Indole moieties are generally found in a large amount of synthetic and natural products. Indole is a well known component of fragrances and the precursor to many pharmaceuticals⁴². Some of the indole derivatives were evaluated for

Fig. 8. Plausible mechanism for formation of thiopyridine.

their biological activities⁴³ such as antiviral, anticancer, antifungal, analgesic, insecticidal activity, antioxidant, anti-diabetic, anti-HIV etc.

Classically, indoles have been synthesized by various methods^{45,46}. The use of more environmental friendly protocols for the synthesis of indole derivatives has been reported which are mentioned below.

Borthakur *et al.*⁴⁶ recently described a fast solvent-less synthesis of 5-hydroxy-benzo[*g*]indole scaffolds is accomplished from $\text{BF}_3\text{-OEt}_2$ as a Lewis acid-catalyzed one-pot reaction of naphthoquinone (1), ω -morpholinoacetophenone (2), and urea (3) under microwave irradiation in an open vessel in a Prolabo Synthwave 402 microwave reactor at 140°C for 5 min at atmospheric pressure to afford 2-(*p*-tolyl)-3-morpholino-5-hydroxybenzo[*g*]indole (4) in 80% yield (Scheme 9). The key step in the synthesis is the Michael addition followed by *in situ* aza cyclization reaction using urea as an environmentally benign source of ammonia and the reaction mechanistic pathways are shown in Fig. 9.

R	R ¹
Ph, 4-MeC ₆ H ₄ , 4-ClC ₆ H ₄ , 4-NO ₂ C ₆ H ₄ etc.	Morpholine, Pyrrolidine, Piperidine

Scheme 9. Microwave-assisted synthesis of 5-hydroxybenzo[*g*]indoles.

Lin *et al.*⁴⁷ have been selected three-component domino reaction of anilines (1), arylglyoxal monohydrates (2) and cyclic 1,3-dicarbonyl compounds (3) as a model substrate for microwave-assisted regioselective synthesis of 3-

Fig. 9. Proposed mechanism for the synthesis of benzo[*g*]indole.

functionalized indole derivatives. This reaction has been carried out in EtOH-H₂O (1:1) solvent medium at 90°C for 40 min in trifluoroacetic acid (TFA) catalytic conditions to give the desired product 3-(6-halo-2-aryl-1*H*-indol-3-yl)-4-hydroxy-6-methyl-2*H*-pyran-2-one (4) was obtained in 74% yield in Scheme 10.

Scheme 10. Synthesis of 3-functionalized indole derivatives under MW-irradiation.

Lin groups has been propose the reaction mechanism shown in Fig. 10 for this novel three-component reaction. Intermediate (I) is obtained through Knoevenagel condensation of arylglyoxal (2) with 4-hydroxy-6-methyl-2*H*-pyran-2-one (3) catalyzed by TFA. The successive Michael addi-

tion of aniline (1) to (I) gives intermediate (II), which undergoes an intramolecular nucleophilic addition reaction followed by loss of water to form the product (4).

Fig. 10. Possible mechanism for the formation of 3-functionalized indole derivatives.

Wang *et al.*⁴⁸ has been established a highly sustainable and efficient three component bicyclization reaction of arylglyoxals (1) with cyclic enaminones (2) and amino acids

new 2-aryl-3,4-dihydro-2*H*-thieno[3,2-*b*]indoles in excellent yields under mild reaction conditions. The thieno[3,2-*b*]indoles were evaluated for their *in vitro* activity against *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* H37Rv (MTB) and multi-drug resistant *M. tuberculosis* (MDR-TB).

A plausible mechanism for the formation of (H) involving a [3,3]-sigmatropic rearrangement of the enehydrazine tautomer (D) to (E) with concomitant cyclization and aromatization with the loss of ammonia is depicted in Fig. 11.

1.2.1f. Five membered triazole and tetrazole derivatives:

The triazole units are three nitrogen atoms containing five membered heterocyclic ring systems. They are classified into two types viz. 1,2,3-triazole and 1,2,4-triazole. Tautomeric form of 1,2,4-triazole are shown in Fig. 12.

Specially, 1,2,4-triazoles and their derivatives are found to be linked with many biological activities like antifungal⁴⁹⁻⁵¹, anticonvulsant^{52,53}, anti-inflammatory⁵⁴⁻⁵⁶, anticancer⁵⁷⁻⁶⁰,

Ar	R ¹
<i>p</i> -Tolyl, PMP, 4-BrPh, 4-FPh, 4-ClPh, Ph.	4-BrPh, 4-FPh, 4-ClPh, 3,4-Cl ₂ Ph, <i>p</i> -Tolyl, Ph, PMP

Scheme 11. Synthesis of functionalized oxazolo[5,4-*b*]indoles under MW-irradiation.

(3) to diverse and functionalized oxazolo[5,4-*b*]indoles (4) with good yield (74–89%) and high diastereoselectivity (up to >99:1). This reaction has been carried out in eco-compatible EtOH solvent medium under microwave irradiation at 80°C for 20 min with multiple bond-forming events including C-C, C-N and C-O bonds to give the desired product (4) in Scheme 11.

A new series of 2-aryl-3,4-dihydro-2*H*-thieno[3,2-*b*]indoles derivatives were synthesized successfully by using 5-aryldihydro-3(2*H*)-thiophenones, and arylhydrazine hydrochloride in a 1:1.3 molar ratio in ethanol assisted by microwave irradiation have been described by Perumal and his co-workers⁴⁴ in Scheme 12. This microwave-assisted facile, efficient and rapid regioselective Fischer indole synthesis of

Ar	X
Ph, 4-OMeC ₆ H ₄ , 4-ClC ₆ H ₄ , 4-MeC ₆ H ₄ , 3-O ₂ NC ₆ H ₄ , 4-FC ₆ H ₄	H, 7-Cl, 7-F

Scheme 12. Microwave-assisted facile regioselective Fischer indole synthesis.

Fig. 11. Plausible mechanism formation of thieno-indoles.

Fig. 12. Tautomerism in 1,2,4-triazole.

and antibacterial etc.^{61–64}. A good number of the triazoles are extensively used as antifungal agents because of their high therapeutic index⁶⁵.

Somagond and Joshi groups⁶⁶ has been designed a series of novel bis-1,2,4-triazolin-3-ones and synthesized by one-pot three-component reaction using 3-aryl-5-methyl-1,3,4-oxadiazol-2(3*H*)-one (1), formamide (2) and dibromo reagent (3) under microwave irradiation in presence of K_2CO_3 at maximum power 150 W for 20–25 min at 125°C in Scheme 13 and the reaction mechanistic pathways are shown in Fig. 13. The newly synthesized bis-1,2,4-triazolin-3-ones have shown excellent activity against all the tested pathogenic fungi with least MIC values in the range of 0.80 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ to 0.20 $\mu\text{g/ml}$.

Scheme 13. Synthesis of bis-1,2,4-triazolin-3-ones under MW-irradiation.

The tetrazole scaffold is a synthetically important scaffold that is extensively used in biochemistry, medicine, pharmacology and found in materials such as explosives, photography, photoimaging chemicals, gas generators, polymers, rocket propellants, and agrochemicals⁶⁷. 1,5-Disubstituted tetrazoles have many importance in application fields and it can acts as bioactive agents^{67c} or drugs such as cilostazol, pentylenetetrazole, and latamoxef etc.

Fig. 13. Possible mechanism for the formation of bis-1,2,4-triazolin-3-ones.

Chandgude and co-workers⁶⁸ has been developed a simple and versatile method of microwave-irradiation for the selective synthesis of substituted 1,5-tetrazole (4) through the reaction between different types of acid chloride or carboxylic acids (1), aliphatic or aromatic amines (2) and $TMSN_3$ (3) in the presence of chlorinating reagents $POCl_3$ and CH_3CN used as a solvent at temperatures 180°C to isolate the desired product in a good yield (70–90%) after a reaction time of 4–5 min in Scheme 14.

1.2.1g. Fused triazine derivatives:

The π -deficient triazines are relevant building block for

R ¹	R ²
Bn	C ₆ H ₅ (CH ₂) ₂
Ph	Ph
Et	CH ₂ = CHCH ₂
<i>p</i> -ClC ₆ H ₄ CH ₂	<i>o</i> -ClC ₆ H ₄
<i>m</i> -CH ₃ OC ₆ H ₄	Ph
C ₆ H ₅ (CH ₂) ₂	Bn
CH ₃ (CH ₂) ₂	CH ₃ (CH ₂) ₂
<i>p</i> -O ₂ NC ₆ H ₄	<i>m,p</i> -(CH ₃ O) ₂ C ₆ H ₃
<i>p</i> -CH ₃ OC ₆ H ₄	<i>p</i> -ClC ₆ H ₄

Scheme 14. Synthesis of 1,5-tetrazole under MW-irradiation.

biological heterocycle molecules, which are commonly used as a commercially dyes⁶⁹, insecticides⁷⁰ and more recently pharmaceutical agents⁷¹.

Lim and Dolzhenko group⁷² has been described an efficient one-pot, three-component reaction for the synthesis of 4-aminoimidazo[1,2-*a*][1,3,5]triazines (**4**), which is also known as 5-aza-7-deaza-isosteres of adenine through the reaction between 2-aminoimidazoles (**1**), triethyl orthoformate (**2**) and cyanamide (**3**) under microwave irradiation at 150°C in AcOEt as a solvent system for 25 min with good yield (71–92%) in Scheme 15.

Ar	C ₆ H ₅ , 4-MeC ₆ H ₄ , 4-FC ₆ H ₄ , 2-ClC ₆ H ₄ , 4-OMeC ₆ H ₄ , 2-ClC ₆ H ₄ , 3-NO ₂ C ₆ H ₄ , 4-ClC ₆ H ₄
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Scheme 15. Synthesis of 7-aryl substituted 4-aminoimidazo[1,2-*a*][1,3,5]triazines under MW-irradiation.

In recent times, Li *et al.*⁷³ has been established a concise and efficient method for the synthesis of a series of *N*-arylamino substituted 1,3,5-triazines (**3**), consist on a base-promoted domino [3+2+1] heterocyclization between aryl amidines (**1**) and aromatic isothiocyanates (**2**) in the presence of NaOH under MW-irradiation. The present synthesis shows attractive properties such as concise one-pot conditions, short reaction periods (15–24 min) and easy purifications with good yields (60–78%) (Scheme 16).

Ar	R
Ph, 4-MeC ₆ H ₄ , 4-ClC ₆ H ₄ , 3-ClC ₆ H ₄ , 4-FC ₆ H ₄ , p-tolyl	Ph, 4-Br, pyridyl, 3-pyridyl, 2-pyrimidyl

Scheme 16. Microwave-assisted one-pot domino heterocyclizations to 1,3,5-triazines.

Lim and Dolzhenko groups⁷⁴ has been established an efficient method successfully applied for the synthesis of

functionalized 4-amino-2-methyl-7-phenylimidazo[1,2-*a*][1,3,5]triazine (**4**) by one-pot three-component reaction using 2-amino-4-phenylimidazole (**1**), triethyl orthoacetate (**2**) and cyanamide (**3**) under microwave irradiation at 160°C for 35 min in ethyl acetate led to obtained the desired compound (**4**) with high yield (61%) in Scheme 17.

Ar	R
Ph, 4-OMePh, 4-FPh, 4-ClPh, 4-MePh, 4-PhPh	Me, Et, Pr, Bu

Scheme 17. Synthesis of 4-amino-2-methyl-7-phenylimidazo[1,2-*a*][1,3,5]triazine derivatives under MW-irradiation.

1.2.1h. Quinoline derivatives:

Quinoline derivatives occur in various natural products, especially in alkaloids and are often used for the design of many synthetic compounds with diverse pharmacological properties⁷⁵. Quinolines and their derivatives are important heterocyclic compounds because of their wide-ranging biological activities such as antimalarial activity⁷⁶, antibacterial⁷⁷ and anticancer⁷⁸ etc.

Kumar *et al.*⁷⁹ has been established an efficient and eco-friendly green approach for the synthesis of functionalized quinolin-4-ylmethoxychromen-2-ones (**5**) and functionalized quinolin-4-ylmethoxychromen-4-ones (**4**) via a one-pot three-component domino reaction of propargylated-flavone (**1**) or coumarin (**1a**) with anilines (**2**) and aldehydes (**3**) under solvent-free and microwave conditions is described using YbCl₃ as Lewis acid catalyst to give the desired products with an excellent yields (80–95%) at 100°C in Scheme 18.

On the basis of the experimental results, Kumar proposed a mechanism for this one-pot synthesis of quinolin-4-ylmethoxychromen-4-ones is depicted in Fig. 14.

Bala *et al.*⁸⁰ have described a new facile, four-component domino reactions of 2-hydroxy-1,4-naphthaquinone, aromatic aldehydes, methyl/ethyl acetoacetate and ammonium acetate in ethanol under microwave irradiation at 120 W and 100°C temperature afforded tetrahydrobenzo[*g*]quinoline-5,10-diones regioselectively in good yields. This reaction went to completion in 10 min affording a higher yield of

Scheme 18. Microwave-assisted synthesis of quinolin-4-ylmethoxychromen-2- and -4-ones.

Reaction of 3-arylamino-5,5-dimethylcyclohex-2-enones (1), aromatic aldehydes (2), and active methylene compounds (3) such as malononitrile or ethyl cyanoacetate in ethanol under controlled microwave irradiation (Scheme 20).

Quinazoline and its derivatives are a class of hetero-aromatic compounds that have drawn much attention because of their biological and pharmaceutical activities⁸².

Rocchi *et al.*⁸³ has been established a one-pot, microwave-assisted protocol for the synthesis of 5,6-dihydroquinazolinones from readily available materials such as chalcones (1), 1,3-dicarbonyl compounds (2), butylamine (3), ammonium formate and formamide (4) via intermediate anthranilate derivatives (5), (6) and (7). In the next step to finish the sequence by a microwave-assisted Von Niemen-

Fig. 14. Possible mechanism for the formation of quinolin-4-ylmethoxychromen-4-ones.

desired products (80–88%) than the classical heating in an oil bath for 4 h in Scheme 19. This transformation presumably proceeds via α,β -unsaturated triketone generation/Michael addition/regioselective annulations via intramolecular condensation domino sequence and the reaction mechanistic pathways are shown in Fig. 15.

Singh and co-workers⁸¹ have investigated a 1,8-diazabicyclo[5.4.0]undec-7-ene (DBU; 5 mol%) catalyzed, one pot, simple, and efficient procedure for the rapid construction of *N*-arylquinoline derivatives via a three-compo-

R	R ¹
Ph, 4-ClC ₆ H ₄ , 4-MeC ₆ H ₄ , 3-BrC ₆ H ₄ , 4-NO ₂ C ₆ H ₄ , 2,4-Cl ₂ C ₆ H ₃	Me, Et

Scheme 19. Microwave-assisted synthesis of tetrahydrobenzo[*g*]quinoline-5,10-diones.

Fig. 15. Proposed mechanism for the formation of tetrahydrobenzo[*g*]quinolines.

Ar	R
Ph, 4-MeC ₆ H ₄ , 4-BrC ₆ H ₄	Ph, 4-Cl, 4-OMe, 4-F, 4-Br, 4-NO ₂ , 3-Cl, 4-OH

Scheme 20. Synthesis of *N*-arylquinolines under microwave irradiation.

towski-type cyclocondensation of (7) with formamide (4) to give dihydroquinazolinones (8). This dihydroquinazolinones were efficiently aromatized in the presence of oxidants *N*-bromosuccinimide in an acetonitrile solution by a microwave-irradiation to give desired product 5,7-diarylquinazolin-4(3*H*)-ones (9) with 56–84% yields (Scheme 21).

1.2.1i. Benz[1,4]oxazepine:

Benzoxazepine is a bi-cyclic heterocyclic compound of a benzene ring fused to an oxazepine ring. Some benzoxazepine derivatives have shown potent biological activities and may be considered as lead molecule for the development of future drugs. It shows the different biological activities especially anti-convulsant⁸⁴ obesity, sleep disorder,

CNS depressant activities⁸⁵ and effective for the treatment of hypertension in man⁸⁶.

Shi *et al.*⁸⁷ have been established a four-component Ugi reaction and microwave-irradiation intramolecular Ullmann etherification for the synthesis of a dibenz[*b,f*][1,4]oxazepine derivatives. The reaction occurs in the two step process. In the first step, four-component Ugi reaction by using of 2-aminophenols (1), isocyanides (2) and 2-bromobenzoic acids (3) or 2-bromobenzaldehydes (4) are carried out in MeOH at 50–60°C for 2–3 days to form a acyclic phenol derivatives (A or B) in 46–90% yields. In the second step, a microwave-assisted intramolecular Ullmann etherification has been used to transform these acyclic U-4CR phenol derivatives (A or B) into the cleft-shaped 6/7/6-fused tricyclic heterocycles. The intramolecular Ullmann diaryl ether formation was catalyzed by 10 mol% of CuI and 30 mol% of *N,N* dimethylglycine hydrochloride (DMG·HCl) in the presence of Cs₂CO₃ under microwave irradiation at 150°C temperature for 30 min to furnish the desire product dibenz[*b,f*][1,4]oxazepin-11(10*H*)-ones (5) and dibenz[*b,f*][1,4]oxazepin-11(10*H*)-carboxamides (6) in (64–100%) yields (Scheme 22).

1.2.1j. Pyrazoles:

N-Arylpyrazoles represent a class of heterocyclic compounds of significant importance for the agrochemical and

Scheme 21. Microwave-assisted synthesis of 5,7-diarylquinazolin-4(3*H*)-ones.

R ¹	R ²	R ³	R ⁴	R ⁵	R ⁶
H, 4-Cl, 4,5-benzo, 4-t-Bu	H, -OMe	Ph, 2-thienyl	Bn, Cy, t-Bu, CH ₂ CO ₂ Et	Ph, Me, H, 2-ClC ₆ H ₄	H, -OMe

Scheme 22. Generation of dibenz[*b,f*][1,4]oxazepine Scaffold under MW-irradiation.

pharmaceutical industries⁸⁸. A few examples, Celecoxib⁸⁹, Rimonabant⁹⁰, Doramapimod⁹¹ and PNU-32945⁹² are marketed drugs or drug-candidates (Fig. 16).

Corre and Busca group has been interested in developing a series of bicyclic heteroaromatics bearing a 4-amino-*N*-arylpyrazole moiety for the sake of biological activities. To this purpose, this chemist group engaged for focused on the

synthesis of tetrasubstituted pyrazoles carrying three different functionalities (nitrile, ester and amine). The synthesis of 4-amino-3-cyano-*N*-arylpyrazoles a based on a Thorpe-Ziegler cyclization as the key step has been achieved using microwave activation.

In the first step, diazotization of the anilines (1) with sodium nitrite in aqueous hydrochloric acid, followed by con-

Fig. 16. Examples of therapeutically relevant *N*-aryl-pyrazoles.

denation with malononitrile in basic medium afforded the corresponding dicyanohydrazone (**2**) in good to excellent yields (60–99%).

This dicyanohydrazone compound used as a reactant in the second step and react with methyl bromoacetate (2.5 equiv.) and K_2CO_3 (2.7 equiv.) in DMF under MW-irradiation (90 W) at $120^\circ C$ affording after 15 min to get the desired product methyl 4-amino-3-cyano-1-phenyl-1*H*-pyrazole-5-carboxylate derivatives (**3**) in good yields (40–83%) in Scheme 23⁹³.

Scheme 23. Microwave-assisted synthesis of methyl 4-amino-3-cyano-1-phenyl-1*H*-pyrazole-5-carboxylate derivatives.

1.2.1k. Pyridines, fused pyridines and its derivatives:

Pyridine is the parent ring system of a large number of naturally occurring products and important industrial, pharmaceutical and agricultural chemicals. Pyridine derivatives exhibited various types of biological activities viz. antimicrobial^{94,95}, antibacterial⁹⁶, antimycobacterial^{97,98}, analgesic antiparkinsonian^{99,100}, antitumoral^{101,102}, cytotoxic¹⁰³, anti-malarial¹⁰⁴ etc.

Zomordbakhsh *et al.*¹⁰⁵ have reported a simple one-pot, three-component reaction between a guanidine (**1**), an acetophenone (**2**) and a chalcone (**3**) under microwave irradiation at 600 W for 4 min under solvent-free conditions leading to Kröhnke pyridine (2,4,6-triarylpyridine) derivatives (**4**) in 92–98% yields (Scheme 24).

Ar ¹	Ar ²	Ar ³
Ph, 4-MeC ₆ H ₄ ,	Ph, 2-MeC ₆ H ₄ ,	Ph, 2-MeC ₆ H ₄ ,
4-ClC ₆ H ₄ ,	4-ClC ₆ H ₄ , 4-COMeC ₆ H ₄ ,	4-ClC ₆ H ₄ ,
4-COMeC ₆ H ₄	4-NO ₂ C ₆ H ₄	4-COMeC ₆ H ₄

Scheme 24. One-pot synthesis of 2,4,6-triarylpyridines under microwave irradiation.

The substituted 2-pyridones have extensive range of pharmacological activities¹⁰⁶ including antiviral, antifungal, anti-inflammatory, cardiotoxic and anticancer antiulcer agents ACE inhibitors and anti-HIV activities and so on. Such attention-grabbing biological applications have fascinated worldwide organic as well as medicinal chemists are engaged to development of efficient and environmentally friendly synthetic methods to access pyridone-bearing pharmacophores¹⁰⁷.

Recently, Bai and his co-workers¹⁰⁸ has been demonstrate that a highly efficient three component domino protocol for the construction of polysubstituted-2-pyridone derivatives by the reaction of 1,3-dicarbonyl compounds (**1**), diethyl ethoxymethylenemalonate (**2**) and amines (**3**) as test substrates. This reaction has been carried out under solvent-free microwave irradiation at $120^\circ C$ for 16 min to give the desired product (**4**) with good yield (86%) in Scheme 25.

Scheme 25. Synthesis of 2-pyridone derivatives under MW-irradiation.

Bai groups have been proposing the plausible reaction mechanism shown in Fig. 17 for this three-component domino reaction. At the start, Intermediate (I) has been obtained through the condensation of 1,3-dicarbonyl compound (1) and amine (3). For the moment, an underwent a process of imine-enamine tautomerization to obtain Intermediate enaminone (II). Then, Intermediate (II) reacted with diethyl ethoxymethylenemalonate (2) to form intermediate (III) via an aza-ene reaction mechanism. Finally, intermediate (III) undergone an intramolecular cyclization and followed by loss of ethanol to form the product (4).

Fig. 17. Possible mechanism for the formation of 2-pyridone derivatives.

1.3. Microwave-assisted non-multicomponent synthesis of heterocycles

Microwave irradiation has significant outcome to promote non-multicomponent reactions. We focus on the heterocycles ring system that is formed in these reaction pathways and which is classified it by the number and types of heteroatoms are present. As a result, the majority of heterocyclic non-multicomponent reaction (only one or two reacting substrate are present) products are nitrogen heterocycles.

1.3a. Pyrroles and its derivatives:

Dembinski and his co-workers¹⁰⁹ have developed a ZnCl₂

is an efficient, ligand-free, non-precious metal catalyst for 5-*endo-dig* cyclization of 1,4- and 1,2,4-substituted but-3-yn-1-yl (homopropargyl) azides in dichloroethane as a solvent at elevated temperature (~130°C) provides 2,5-di- and 2,3,5-trisubstituted pyrroles in high to moderate yields (91–41%) in Scheme 26. This microwave-assisted protocol provides a facile preparation of *N*-unprotected highly substituted pyrroles with aryl, (fused) cycloalkyl, and alkyl groups.

R	R ¹
H, -OMe, -Cl, -F	Ph, 4-MeC ₆ H ₄ , -Cyclopropyl, -Cyclohexene, -C ₃ H ₇

Scheme 26. Microwave-assisted synthesis of substituted pyrroles from homopropargyl azides.

The zinc-catalyzed formation of *N*-unprotected highly substituted pyrroles from homopropargyl azides is believed to proceed via an intramolecular, stepwise mechanism (Fig. 18). In view of the fact that non-terminal alkynes have used in this work and the mechanistic pathway can be illustrated using the coordination of Zn to carbon-carbon triple bond. However, activation via coordination of Zn to nitrogen cannot be excluded. Required higher temperature as compared to Au/Ag or Pt may indicate lower Zn ability to stabilize a cyclic cationic intermediate.

Fig. 18. Plausible mechanism formation of *N*-unprotected substituted pyrroles.

A facile and efficient method to synthesize ring fused pyrrole in a single operation by the reaction of 1,3-diketone

R	R ¹
Ph, 4-MeC ₆ H ₄ , 4-ClC ₆ H ₄ , 4-OMeC ₆ H ₄ , 3,4,5-OMeC ₆ H ₄ , 2,4-OMeC ₆ H ₄ etc. 2,4-OMeC ₆ H ₄ etc.	Ph, 4-MeC ₆ H ₄ , 4-ClC ₆ H ₄ , 4-OMeC ₆ H ₄ , 3,4,5-OMeC ₆ H ₄ ,

Scheme 27. Microwave-assisted synthesis of pyrrole derivatives.

and cyclic secondary amine under MW-irradiation at 280°C in the presence of 0.5 equivalent of *p*-toluenesulfoic acid (*p*-TSA) with 53% yield (Scheme 27) in 10 min has been described by Deb *et al.*¹¹⁰ and the reaction mechanistic pathways are shown in Fig. 19.

Fig. 19. Proposed mechanism for the formation of amide and pyrrole.

The energy efficiency of microwave-assisted reactions has been studied under heterogeneous catalytic condition such as semi-synthetic clay montmorillonite K-10 produced from natural montmorillonites by treatment with diluted mineral acid. This material absorbs microwave energy effectively and is a superb catalyst for microwave-assisted organic synthesis. It is a commercially available, noncorrosive, inexpensive, stable and easily reusable solid¹¹¹. Montmorillonite K-10 has a substantial surface area (~250 m² g⁻¹) and a Hammett acidity constant of ($H_0 \approx -8$), which corresponds approximately to the acidity of concentrated nitric acid.

Török *et al.*^{112a,b} has been performed the model reaction hexane-2,5-dione was used as a cyclialkylating agent with anilines in a solvent-free K-10-catalyzed reaction for the syn-

thesis of 2,5-dimethyl-1-arylpyrroles at 90°C under microwave condition in 1 min reaction time get excellent yields (~99%) in Scheme 28.

Scheme 28. Synthesis of 2,5-dimethyl-1-arylpyrroles under microwave irradiation.

1.3b. Indoles, 2*H*-indazole and its derivatives:

A facile and efficient method to synthesize of differently substituted indoles via microwave-assisted cycloisomerization of 2-alkynylaniline derivatives in water at 200°C to give moderate to good yields (26–77%) has been described by Carpita *et al.*¹¹³. This reactions are run without any metal catalyst, acid, or base, and do not take place by applying conventional heating (Scheme 29).

R	R ¹
H, Ph, 4-OMeC ₆ H ₅ , 4-ClC ₆ H ₅ , 4-MeC ₆ H ₅	H, -OMe, -Cl, Me, -COCH ₃

Scheme 29. Microwave-assisted cycloisomerization of 2-phenyl-ethynylaniline.

Carpita and Ribecai groups¹¹⁴ have reported an efficient methodology for the preparation of differently substituted in-

doles and azindoles via microwave-assisted cycloisomerization in water of 2-alkynylanilines and alkynylpyridinamines, which is promoted by catalytic amounts of neutral or basic salts or by stoichiometric weak organic bases in good to high yields (45-66%) without any added metal catalyst in 15-30 min, and did not take place by applying conventional heating (Scheme 30).

R	R ¹	Neutral salt /Basic or Acid salt
H, Ph, 4-ClC ₆ H ₄ , 4-OMeC ₆ H ₄ , Pyridine.	H, -OMe, -Cl, -COCH ₃ , CN, Me.	KCl, KBr, LiCl, NaCl, (<i>n</i> -Bu) ₄ NCl, NaOH, NaHCO ₃ , NH ₄ Cl, KOH, K ₂ CO ₃

Scheme 30. Microwave-assisted cycloisomerization of 2-aminophenyl-alkyne derivatives.

Scheme 32. Synthesis of homofascaplysin C and fascaplysin.

Török *et al.*^{112a} has been performed the model reaction hexane-2,5-dione was used as a cyclialkylating agent with substituted pyrrole in a solvent-free K-10-catalyzed reaction for the synthesis of 4,7-dimethylindole at 90^oC under microwave condition in 60 min reaction time get excellent yields (80–81%) in Scheme 31.

Waldmann *et al.*¹¹⁵ described a silver-catalyzed and MW-assisted one-pot cascade reaction sequence that gives access to different alkaloid-inspired polycyclic scaffold classes including fascaplysin-type alkaloids (52%) and their analogs

Scheme 31. Synthesis of 4,7-dimethylindole under microwave irradiation.

(53%) in Scheme 32.

Kaur and his co-workers¹¹⁶ has been described the organocatalytic microwave-irradiation reaction between isatin derivatives (1) and 2,4-dinitrotoluene (2) in ethanol in the presence of 1 mol% of 1,8-diazabicyclo[5.4.0]undec-7-ene (DBU) as a catalyst to produced variety of 3-substituted 3-hydroxy-2-oxindoles (3) in 1 min and up to 99% conversion (determined by HPLC analysis) in Scheme 33.

1.3c. 2H-indazole:

Indazoles being *N*-heterocycles, are gaining a lot of im-

R ¹	R ²
H, CH ₂ C ₆ H ₅ , CH ₂ CHCH ₂ , Me	H, Cl, Br, I, Me, OMe, F

Scheme 33. Synthesis of 3-substituted 3-hydroxy-2-oxindoles under MW-irradiation.

portance in the field of medicinal and organic chemistry as they exhibit a broad spectrum of pharmacological and biological activities¹¹⁷. 2*H*-Indazoles are widely used in pharma sector than 1*H*-indazoles due to their potent bioactivities like anti-tumor¹¹⁸, anti-microbial¹¹⁹, anti-inflammatory¹²⁰, HIV protease Inhibition¹²¹ etc. Vidyacharan *et al.*¹²² has been performed the reaction between 2-azidobenzaldehyde with various amines like aromatic, heteroaromatic, aliphatic and benzylic amines, aniline under catalyst- and solvent-free conditions at 140°C under microwave condition to offered wide range of 2*H*-indazoles in excellent yields (86–97%) (Scheme 34).

R ¹	R ²
H, 5-Br, 6-Br	Ph, 2,3-Me ₂ C ₆ H ₄ , 2-BrC ₆ H ₄ , Cyclohexyl, pyridine, -CH ₂ Ph etc.

Scheme 34. Synthesis of 2*H*-indazole under microwave irradiation.

1.3d. Pyrimidines and its derivatives:

Radhakrishnan and co-workers¹²³ has been described a one-pot synthesis of a series of 2-amino-4-pyrimidinones, by treatment of the corresponding β -ketoester or β -aldehydoester with guanidine hydrochloride in the presence of K₂CO₃, in a microwave-assisted method without the requirement of solvent. The synthesized isocytosines vary in their substitutions at C-5 and C-6 positions (Scheme 35).

R ¹	R ²
H, Me, Et, -CHMe ₂ , Ph	H, -CHMe ₂ , -CH ₂ Ph, Ph, -CH ₂ C ₁₀ H ₇

Scheme 35. Synthesis of 2-amino-4-pyrimidinones under microwave irradiation.

The precursor of pyrimidine has captured an important place in nucleic acid chemistry. Pyrimidine derivatives including uracil, thymine, cytosine, adenine, and guanine are fundamental building blocks for deoxyribonucleic acid (DNA) and

ribonucleic acid (RNA) and give informations that pyrimidine derivatives exhibit varied pharmacological activity as well as anticancer activity is most extensively reported¹²⁴. Some pyrimidine derivatives which are commercially available in the market as anticancer drugs such as clofarabine, gemcitabine, fluorouracil, tegafur, uramustine, decitabine¹²⁵ (Fig. 20).

Fig. 20. Examples of pyrimidine derivatives anticancer drugs.

Hosamani *et al.*¹²⁶ has been performed the reaction between substituted chalconated coumarin with 2-(4-fluorophenyl) acetamide hydrochloride in 5 mL DMF as a solvent, at 120°C temperature under both conventional and microwave irradiation method to offered wide range of 3-(2-(4-fluorobenzyl)-6-(substituted phenyl)pyrimidin-4-yl)-2*H*-chromen-2-one derivatives. The synthesis of the target molecules was carried out as outlined in Scheme 36. From experimental observation, this chemist group has been reported that microwave irradiation method to provide good to excellent yields (74–91%) as compared to conventional method (53–67%).

The synthesized compounds were evaluated for their anticancer activity against two human cancer cell lines viz. A-549 (human lung carcinoma) and MDA-MB-231 (human adenocarcinoma mammary gland). The results revealed that several synthesized compounds exhibit significant cytotoxicity against the two tested cancer cell lines with IC₅₀ < 10 mM from cell study they have been observed that compound 3-(2-(4-fluorobenzyl)-6-(4-Cl-phenyl)pyrimidin-4-yl)-2*H*-chromen-2-one derivative exhibited potent activity against the A-549 cell line, which is comparable with standard drug *Cisplatin*, whereas compound 3-(2-(4-fluorobenzyl)-6-(4-OMe-phenyl) pyrimidin-4-yl)-2*H*-chromen-2-one derivatives was found extremely active against the MDA-MB-231 cell line and proved to be more potent than standard drug *Cisplatin*.

R	4-Me, 4-OMe, 3-Me, 3-OMe, 2-Me, 2-OMe, 4-Br, 3-Br, 2-Br, 4-Cl, 3-Cl, 2-Cl
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Scheme 36. Microwave-assisted synthesis of fluorinated coumarin-pyrimidine derivatives.

Ar	C ₆ H ₅ , 4-MeC ₆ H ₄ , 4-FC ₆ H ₄ , 2-MeC ₆ H ₄ , 4-OMeC ₆ H ₄ , 2-OMeC ₆ H ₄ , 4-CF ₃ C ₆ H ₄ , 4-CNC ₆ H ₄
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Scheme 37. Synthesis of 7-substituted pyrazolo[1,5-a]pyrimidines via Pd-catalyzed under MW-irradiation.

Bassoude and his co-workers¹²⁷ have been developed a one-pot synthesis of 7-substituted pyrazolo[1,5-a]pyrimidines via Pd-catalyzed direct CH-arylation followed by saponification-decarboxylation under microwave irradiation at 150–158°C temperature to isolate the desired product in a good yield (82%) after a shorter reaction time of 30 min in Scheme 37.

1.3e. Imidazoles and its derivatives:

Alzieu and his co-workers¹²⁸ have been demonstrated the microwave-assisted reaction of variety of alkylamines (1) with 4- and 5-aryloxazoles (2) in solvent system like *o*-dichlorobenzene (*o*-DCB) in presence of TFA (2 equivalent) at 200°C temperature to produce the desired product 1-alkyl-4-aryl- and 1-alkyl-5-arylimidazoles (3) in reproducibly good yield (79%) (Scheme 38).

The formation of imidazole would involve attack at C2 of an oxazolium intermediate by the amine, followed by ring

R ¹	R ²	R ³
H, Ph, F, 4-MeC ₆ H ₄	H, Ph, 3,4-FCF ₃ C ₆ H ₃	Cyclohexyl, cyclopentyl, cyclopropenyl, Benzyl, n-pentyl

Scheme 38. Synthesis of 1-alkyl-4-aryl- and 1-alkyl-5-arylimidazoles under MW-irradiation.

opening/closing and extrusion of water in Fig. 21.

Kumar *et al.*¹²⁹ has been reported a new route for the construction of 2-aminoimidazolidines including analogues of the α_2 adrenergic agonist drug clonidine is elaborated.

Fig. 21. Proposed mechanism for the formation of 1-alkyl-4-aryl- and 1-alkyl-5-aryl imidazoles.

Scheme 39. One-pot synthesis of 2-aminoimidazolines under microwave irradiation.

The important step is an intramolecular microwave-assisted Staudinger/aza-Wittig cyclization of an *in situ* generated urea intermediate (formed by the reaction of β -amino azide and isocyanate) upon treatment with Bu_3P or polymer-supported phosphine reagent, allowing the introduction of various substituents at the N1 and the 2-amino function in Scheme 39.

1.3f. Pyridines, fused pyridines and its derivatives:

A new method allowing the preparation of highly functionalized pyridine derivatives was established by Linder and his co-workers¹³⁰. In this synthesis, the reaction between the 6*H*-1,2-oxazine (**1**) and various alkynes (**2**) was performed in the presence of $BF_3 \cdot Et_2O$ in 1,2-dichloroethane at 70°C under microwave irradiation conditions, the expected polyfunctionalized pyridine (**3**) was formed in excellent yield 67% (Scheme 40) and the reaction mechanistic pathways are shown (Fig. 22).

R	R ¹	R ²	R ³
Me, Et	H, Me	H, Me, C ₆ H ₅ , p-methoxybenzyl	C ₆ H ₅ , C ₆ H ₅ S, Cyclopropyl

Scheme 40. Microwave-assisted synthesis polyfunctionalized pyridine.

Fig. 22. Probable mechanism for the formation of polyfunctionalized pyridine.

Yang and Jiang research group¹³¹ have designed a series of furo[3,2-*b*]pyridines via a base-promoted regioselective transannulation between *N*-aryl 4-aminofuran-2(5*H*)-ones (**1**) and 1,3-diaryl-2,3-epoxypropan-1-ones (**2**) under microwave (MW) heating at 60°C in DMF solvent. This 4-aminopyrrol-2(5*H*)-ones (**1**) undergoes formal [3+3] cycloaddition reaction gave two different type of products depending on the electronic properties of the substituents on the aniline moiety of the 4-aminopyrrol-2(5*H*) ones. If an electron-withdrawing group (EWG) are present in the *N*-aryl 4-aminopyrrol-2(5*H*)-ones moiety, it provide a high yield (40–80%) of the desired product pyrrolo[3,2-*b*]pyridines (**3**), whereas their counterparts with an electron-neutral (ENG) and -donating (EDG) substituents preferred a different reaction pathway to form new polyfunctionalized pyrrolo[3,2-*b*]pyrroles (**4**) with a high yield (62–76%) through C-C bond cleavage (Scheme 41).

Yang group has been draw a plausible mechanistic pathways to products where the nucleophilic addition of *N*-aryl 4-aminofuran-2(5*H*)-ones (**1**) ($Ar^1 = EWG$) to β -position of oxiranes (**2**) in the presence of base generates intermediate (**A**) followed by H-transfer and intramolecular Knoevenagel condensation to afford the final fused pyridines (**3**) (Fig. 23)¹³¹.

In this mechanistic pathways at first strong base uses for

Ar ¹	Ar ²	Ar ³
4-ClC ₆ H ₄ , 4-BrC ₆ H ₄ , 4-MeC ₆ H ₄ , 4-OMeC ₆ H ₄ , 4-FC ₆ H ₄ , 3,4-Cl ₂ C ₆ H ₃	C ₆ H ₅ , 4-ClC ₆ H ₄ , 4-BrC ₆ H ₄ ,	Ph, 4-ClC ₆ H ₄ , 4-OMeC ₆ H ₄ 2,4-Cl ₂ C ₆ H ₃ , 2,3-Cl ₂ C ₆ H ₃

Scheme 41. Microwave-assisted synthesis of substituted fused pyridines and pyrroles.

Fig. 23. Possible mechanism for the formation of pyrrolo[3,2-*b*]pyridines (3) derivatives.

the desired product pyrrolo[3,2-*b*]pyrroles (4) through tautomerization (Fig. 24)¹³¹.

Phenanthridinone is one of the structural units of various natural products and pharmaceuticals with a broad range of biological activities such as antitumour, antiviral, antileukemic, antifungal, antiprotozoal etc. (Fig. 25)¹³². Correspondingly, dihydrophenanthridines though less abundant in nature exhibit biological activities comparable to that of phenanthridines¹³³.

Now a day's most of the chemists are successfully utilized the natural products as reagents or catalysts in organic

Fig. 24. Possible mechanism for the formation of pyrrolo[3,2-*b*]pyrroles (4) derivatives.

activate the *N*-aryl 4-aminofuran-2(5*H*)-ones (1) (Ar¹ = EDG or ENG), which undergoes 1,3-*H* transfer to form intermediate (C). This intermediate (C) facilitates aldol-type reaction of oxiranes (2), providing adduct intermediate (D). In the next step, the *N*-position of adduct intermediate (D) attacks selectively on the α -position of oxiranes (2) in an intramolecular manner to give an intermediate (E). This intermediate (E) releases an aryl aldehyde and an hydroxyl anion to yield pyrrolo[3,2-*b*]pyrrole intermediate (F), which converted into

Fig. 25. Phenanthridinone and dihydrophenanthridine based natural products.

transformations¹³⁴. Vasicine is a quinazoline alkaloid present abundantly in the leaves of *Adhatoda vasica* vasicine as an efficient organocatalyst for coupling^{77a} and also participate in reduction reactions^{134c}.

Sharma *et al.*¹³⁵ have been developed an efficient and transition metal-free process for the synthesis of phenanthridinones and dihydrophenanthridines by utilizing vasicine as a catalyst via intramolecular C-H arylation with aryl halides in the presence of KOtBu as a base under microwave irradiation at 120°C temperature in sulfolane as a solvent system for 15 min, providing the desired products in (45–90%) yields (Scheme 42) and the reaction mechanistic pathways are shown (Fig. 26).

Scheme 42. Synthesis of phenanthridinones and dihydrophenanthridines under MW-irradiation.

Fig. 26. Possible mechanism for the formation of phenanthridinones.

Rodrigues-Santos *et al.*¹³⁶ have reported the synthesis of pyrazolo[3,4-*b*]pyridin-6-ones both by the conventional method and by MW irradiation (Scheme 43). The desired product (**A**) were obtained in moderate to good yields (50–85%) using the conventional methanol reflux method in 4–24 h. Using this MW method, product (**A**) were produced in moderate yield (50–65%), which is low compared to the conventional methodology, but is 90 times faster than conventional method.

Scheme 43. Synthesis of pyrazolo[3,4-*b*]pyridin-6-ones under MW irradiation.

1.3g. Pyrazolopyrazine and its fused derivatives:

A synthetic route to novel fused pyrazolo[3,4-*b*]pyrazine derivatives (**3**) has been described by Quiroga and Sánchez groups¹³⁷ which proceeds through a MW-induced cyclocondensation of *ortho*-aminonitrosopyrazoles (**1**) and cyclic β -diketones (**2**) in DMF (Scheme 44). This protocol provides a simple procedure for the synthesis of the title compounds with the advantages of easy work-up, mild reaction conditions and good yields.

R ¹	R ²
CH ₃ , (CH ₃) ₃ C	H, 4-Cl, 4-Br, 4-CN

Scheme 44. Microwave-assisted synthesis of fused pyrazolo[3,4-*b*]pyrazine derivatives.

The above mention reaction is initiated by chemo-selective addition of the enol tautomer of the diketone to the nitroso group of the pyrazole, resulting in formation of an imine. This intermediate undergoes an intramolecular *N*-cyclization involving the amino group (NH₂) of the pyrazole and the remaining carbonyl group (Fig. 27).

Fig. 27. Possible mechanism for the formation of fused pyrazolopyrazines.

1.3h. Triazine derivatives:

Bigot *et al.*¹³⁸ have been proposed a newly synthesized 1,2,4-triazine derivatives (**B**) in excellent yields (62–92%) by

the reaction of oxazolines (**A**) with excess of hydrazine hydrochloride in methanol under MW-irradiation for 1 h at 90°C (Scheme 45).

R ¹	R ²
C ₆ H ₅ , 3-Pyridyl, -CO ₂ Me	H, Ph, Et, Phenylacetylene

Scheme 45. Microwave-assisted synthesis of 5,5-disubstituted-1,2,4-triazines.

Pleasantly, the microwave irradiation of (**C**) in EtOH in the presence of BF₃·OEt₂ allowed the formation of (**D**) in 55% isolated yields (Fig. 28).

Fig. 28. Regioselective functionalization of (**C**) at C5.

Moody and co-workers¹³⁹ have been disclosed the synthesis of 1,2,4-triazines using a new two-step sequence for the conversion of hydrazides (**1**) to triazines (**3**). The key steps are *N*-H insertion by a copper carbene intermediate derived from α -diazo- β -ketoesters (**2**) into the hydrazide, followed by reaction with ammonium acetate to give the desired product trifluoromethyl-1,2,4-triazines (**3**) in moderate to good yields (28–91%) (Scheme 46).

Scheme 46. Two-step synthesis of 1,2,4-triazines under microwave irradiation.

Insuasty *et al.*¹⁴⁰ have described a new series of novel 4-hetaryl substituted pyrazolo[1,5-*a*][1,3,5]triazines were synthesized by microwave assisted reaction between *O,S*-di-

ethyl hetaroylimidothiocarbonates and 5-amino-3-aryl-1*H*-pyrazoles under solvent-free conditions in Scheme 47.

Het.	Ar
2-furyl, 2-thienyl	C ₆ H ₅ , 4-ClC ₆ H ₄ , 4-MeC ₆ H ₄

Scheme 47. Microwave-assisted synthesis of 4-hetarylpyrazolo[1,5-a][1,3,5]triazines.

1.3i. Benzotriazole derivatives:

Kokel *et al.*¹⁴¹ have been reported a novel microwave-assisted solid acid catalyzed method for the synthesis of substituted 1,2,3-benzotriazoles via an *in situ* solid phase diazotation protocol and subsequent intramolecular cyclization of *o*-phenylenediamines in Scheme 48. In addition, K-10 has a high surface area, about 250–300 m² g⁻¹, is stable under high temperature conditions and have strong microwave absorption capability making it an ideal catalyst and suitable medium for solvent-free microwave-assisted reactions. The catalyst is recyclable, and the reaction occurs with high efficiency and does not produce any harmful waste.

R ¹	H, Me, 5,6-dichloro, 4,5-dimethyl, 5-CF ₃ , 5-Cl, 5-Cl-6-F, 5,6-dimethyl
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Scheme 48. Synthesis of 1,2,3-benzotriazoles under MW-irradiation.

Kokel *et al.* proposed a possible mechanism of the formation of 1,2,3-benzotriazoles via a microwave-assisted K-10 montmorillonite catalyzed solid phase diazotation and subsequent cyclization reaction of *o*-phenylenediamine (Fig. 29).

1.3j. Isoquinoline and their derivatives:

Isoquinoline are benzopyridines, which are composed of a benzene ring fused to a pyridine ring isoquinoline analogs of the cancer drug clinical candidate tipifarnib. These compounds kill *Trypanosoma cruzi* amastigotes grown in mammalian host cells at concentrations in the low nanomolar

Fig. 29. Possible mechanism for the formation of 1,2,3-benzotriazoles.

range. These isoquinolines represent new leads for the development of drugs to treat Chagas disease¹⁴².

Kokui *et al.*¹⁴³ have been reported a novel microwave-assisted Friedel-Crafts Type Cyclization Reaction for the synthesis of isoquinolone derivatives by using of azide as starting substrate in presence of decalin as a solvent and tributylamine as a base at 190°C temperature for 60 min to give the desired product with good yields in Scheme 49.

R = H, 4-Cl, 4-Me, 4-OMe, 4-Br, 4-NO₂

Scheme 49. Synthesis of isoquinolone derivatives under MW-irradiation.

Xu *et al.*¹⁴⁴ has been represented a novel approach for the synthesis of isoxazoline-functionalized isoquinolines via the TBHP (*t*-BuOOH) as an oxidant and *n*-Bu₄Ni (TBAI) catalyzed radical cascade cyclization of vinyl isocyanides (**1**) with β,γ -unsaturated ketoximes (**2**) under microwave irradiation at 80°C for 30 min in MeCN (solvent) led to obtained the desired compound (**3**) with high yield (57–91%) (Scheme 50).

Xue and his coworkers¹⁴⁵ has been explained a convenient microwave-assisted efficient protocol for the synthesis of hydroxyl-containing isoquinolines from a metal-free radical cyclization reaction of methyl 2-isocyano-3,3-diphenylacrylate (**1**) with isopropanol (**2**) in the presence of radical

Scheme 50. Synthesis of isoxazoline-functionalized isoquinolines under MW-irradiation.

Fig. 30. Possible radical mechanism for the formation of isoxazoline-functionalized isoquinolines.

initiator tertbutyl peroxybenzoate (TBPB) and DBU as a base under heating condition at 120°C for 1 h to give the desired product methyl 1-(2-hydroxypropan-2-yl)-4-phenyl-isoquinoline-3-carboxylate (**3**) was obtained in (72–94%) yield (Scheme 51).

R ¹	R ²	R ³
H, F, OMe, Cl, Br, Me	C ₆ H ₅ , 4-MeC ₆ H ₄ , 2-ClC ₆ H ₄ , Cyclohexyl	OMe, OEt, Piperidine, pyrrolidine

Scheme 51. Synthesis of alkyl-1-(2-hydroxypropan-2-yl)-4-phenyl-isoquinoline-3-carboxylate under MW-irradiation.

1.3k. 5 and 6-membered N-heterocycles:

The polarized ketene dithioketals **1** (Fig. 31) have been familiar as useful building blocks in many synthetic organic transformations. They can be converted into the corresponding *S,N*- and *N,N*-ketals, **2** and **3**, respectively, making them important as precursors for a large variety of functionalized ketals¹⁴⁶.

The ketene dithioketals have also been used as intermediates for the synthesis of several *N*-heterocycles, which

Fig. 31. Ketene dithioketals **1**, *S,N*- and *N,N*-ketals **2** and **3**, respectively.

have different biological properties, such as enzyme inhibition^{147a,b}, insecticides^{147c} and tuberculostatic activity^{147d}. More recently, the bis-vinyl substitution of 1,1-bis(methylthio)-2-nitroethylene with diamines or hydroxylamines has been reported for the synthesis of 5-member or 6-member nitrovinyl derivatives^{147e}.

Sangi *et al.*¹⁴⁸ has been reported the reaction of 1,1-bis(thiomethyl)-2-nitroethylene (**2**) with a range of alkyldiamines and hydroxylalkylamines in presence of ethanol to

afforded five and six membered *N*-heterocycles in good yields under microwave irradiation represented (Scheme 52).

Scheme 52. Synthesis of 5 and 6-membered *N*-heterocycles under microwave irradiation.

1.3l. Thiadiazine-1-oxides derivatives:

The modular one-pot novel microwave-assisted, $\text{Cp}^*\text{Co}^{\text{III}}$ -catalyzed direct C-H activation/double C-N bond formation reaction of simple NH-sulfoximines with 1,4,2-dioxazol-5-ones as the amination reagent in presence of anion counterpart of the silver salt AgNTf_2 under the mixture solvent of *t*-AmOH/ CHCl_3 (1:1) at 100°C temperature for 2–3 h to produce diverse thiadiazine-1-oxides in moderate to excellent yields up to (87%) has been reported by Huang *et al.*¹⁴⁹ (Scheme 53) and the reaction mechanistic pathways are shown (Fig. 32).

Scheme 53. Synthesis of thiadiazine-1-oxides under MW-irradiation.

1.3m. Quinazoline derivatives:

Quinazoline has two fused six-membered simple aromatic rings, a benzene ring and a pyrimidine ring having due to its manifold uses. Numerous quinazoline derivatives have broad

Fig. 32. Possible mechanism for the formation of thiadiazine-1-oxides.

spectrum of biological activities like anti-bacterial, antifungal analgesic, anticancer, anti-hypertensive, anti-HIV, anti-inflammatory, antioxidant, anti-microbial, analgesic, anticonvulsant and antimalarial activities¹⁵⁰.

Kumar and Singh group¹⁵¹ has been developed a novel and efficient metal free synthetic protocol for obtaining benzimidazo[1,2-*a*]quinazolines, via a one-pot reaction of *N*-(2-benzimidazolyl)-2-aminobenzamide (1) with 2-halobenzaldehyde (2) or 2-chloroquinoline-3-carbaldehydes (3) in the presence of Na_2CO_3 as base in DMF as solvent, under microwave irradiation at 130°C for 5 min to obtained desired products (4 and 5) with a moderate to good yields (60–77%) (Scheme 54).

Scheme 54. Synthesis of benzimidazo[1,2-*a*]quinazoline derivatives under MW-irradiation.

A plausible mechanism for this consecutive metal-free C-N bond formation/cleavage protocol is outlined (Fig. 33).

Step 1: Formation of 3-(1*H*-benzo[*d*]imidazole-2-yl)-2-(2-bromophenyl)-2,3-dihydroquinazoline-4(1*H*)-one (**A**) through a conventional cyclization process.

Step 2: Na₂CO₃ as base-promoted intramolecular addition/elimination reaction leading to the formation of a new C-N bond in intermediate (**B**).

Step 3: This intermediate (**B**) undergoes cleavage of the amide bond in the presence of Na₂CO₃ and H₂O to obtain another intermediate (**C**).

Step 4: Finally the second C-N bond cleavage of the intermediate (**C**) followed by base to deliver the desired product (**5**).

1.3n. Thiazole and aminothiazole:

The 2-aminothiazole ring is an important heterocyclic skeleton that has found wide application in organic and medicinal chemistry. Thiazole and aminothiazole scaffolds have been documented as privileged structural motifs in medicinal chemistry. Several drug molecules gifted with effective biological activity against allergies, hypertension, bacterial, inflammation, cancer, schizophrenia, and viral infections contain a 2-aminothiazole moiety¹⁵². A lot of number of methodologies for the synthesis of 2-aminothiazole derivatives has been published in reputed journals¹⁵³ but another new types of methodologies has been discovered by Scalacci group.

Scalacci *et al.*¹⁵⁴ have been reported a simple and versatile method of microwave-irradiation for the selective syn-

Fig. 33. Possible mechanism for the formation of benzimidazo[1,2-*a*]quinazoline derivatives.

Scheme 55. Synthesis of 2-aminothiazoles and 2-amino-4-methylenethiazolines under MW-irradiation.

thesis of 2-aminothiazoles (**A**) through the reaction between propargylamines (**1**) and isothiocyanates (**2**) in the presence of catalytic PTSA at temperatures above 130–160°C and in a few minutes. But the same reaction carried out at lower temperatures (100–130°C) leads to the formation of the tautomeric 2-amino-4-methylenethiazolines (**B**) in Scheme 55.

Conclusion

Microwave-irradiation is a good useful technique in the field of synthetic organic chemistry and governs a comfortable platform for *N*-containing heterocycle ring formation. This review has highlighted the application of microwave irradiation on the development of innovative and efficient synthetic approaches for the generation of *N*-containing five to seven-membered heterocycles and their fused analogues over the past decade. This irradiation technique enables a huge number of organic reactions to be successfully completed under mild reaction condition, has a profound affect on reaction rates and purity and with higher yields in comparison to conventional heating. Few examples described in this review illustrate that cycloaddition and cyclization reactions take place under microwave irradiation, has been dramatically enhanced over classical heating. The one-pot multi-component cyclization reactions that carried out with the elimination of a small molecule such as water are particularly stimulated by microwave irradiations which are commonly used to construct *N*-heterocyclic rings. We think that in the coming future numerous MW assisted reactions could be done on industrial scales thereby increasing the overall efficiency of the processes and continue to attract much attention in organic synthesis applications. We sincerely believe that this review would be found useful by researchers interested in this field of work.

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Karmakar *et al.*: Microwave irradiation in organic synthesis towards the construction of biologically active *N*-heterocycles

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